

Harnessing AI and Data-Intensive Technologies

Deliverable 2.4: Risk Assessment and Management Models - Version 1

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Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
AIA	Artificial Intelligence Act
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation
DC	Doctoral Candidate
DGA	Data Governance Act
DMA	Digital Markets Act
DORA	Digital Operational Resilience Act
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPV	Data Privacy Vocabulary
DSA	Digital Services Act
FRIA	Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
LLM	Large Language Models
ML	Machine Learning
NIST	U.S. National Institute of Standards and Technology
NIS2	Network and Information Security Directive
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OWL	Web Ontology Language
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Context and Motivation

The rapid expansion of artificial intelligence (AI) and data-intensive technologies has led to a comprehensive framework of European Union regulations, including the AI Act, GDPR, Data Governance Act, Digital Services Act, NIS2, DORA, and the Cyber Resilience Act. Central to all of these overlapping legal instruments is a rigorous, cumulative set of compliance obligations anchored around the continuous identification, assessment, and management of risk.

While a parallel body of technical standards (such as ISO 31000, ISO/IEC 23894, and ISO/IEC 42001) has evolved to assist organizations, these standards operate at high levels of abstraction and do not map straightforwardly onto regulatory requirements. Organizations face a substantial "translation problem" trying to bridge the gap between abstract legal mandates and operational practices. Deliverable 2.4 addresses this challenge by leveraging semantic web technologies to provide machine-readable, interoperable, and validatable representations that support automated audit and compliance checking of the risk management obligation in Article 9 of the AI Act.

This deliverable builds on deliverable 2.2 (Lecat et al., 2026) of the project, a survey of methods and tools for compliance with European AI and data regulation, by considering its findings on semantic technologies and applying them to create the application profile developed in section 5.

Key Contributions

To answer the core research question of how the risk management requirements in Article 9 of the EU AI Act can be modelled using semantic web technologies, the deliverable makes three primary contributions:

1. *Systematic Conceptual Analysis of Risk*: The report establishes a clear theoretical distinction between two definitional traditions: the deviation-from-objectives tradition (found in organizational standards like ISO 31000) and the harm-oriented tradition (centric to EU regulations targeting impacts on third parties and protected interests). It maps out the layered ISO/IEC standard architecture and differentiates between risk assessments and impact assessments.
2. *Evaluation and Selection of Semantic Models*: The deliverable performs a structured comparative evaluation of ten existing semantic risk management models against six criteria. Based on this analysis, the Data Privacy Vocabulary is selected as the primary general semantic foundation.
3. *Development of AI Act Application Profile*: Grounded in the LOT (Linked Open Terms) methodology, the report extracts 27 atomic, lifecycle-spanning regulatory requirements directly from Article 9 of the AI Act (governing high-risk AI systems). These requirements are

operationalized via corresponding clauses in ISO 31000 and ISO/IEC 23894, translated into DPV concepts, and encoded into SHACL (Shapes Constraint Language) shapes.

Practical Impact and Future Work

The resulting application profile has been made open-source on GitHub and integrated into an interactive web application, allowing practitioners to upload semantic risk management files and automatically check them for regulatory completeness and compliance.

As part of the iterative progression of Work Package 2 of the HARNES project, a future version of this deliverable (slated for late 2027) will expand the application profile to cover adjacent legislation like the GDPR, and provide an application of the resources developed here to case studies.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The proliferation of artificial intelligence and data-intensive technologies across sectors and societies has led to a corresponding surge in regulatory activity, particularly within the European Union. Over the past several years, the EU has adopted (or substantially advanced) a number of legal instruments that together represent a framework for the governance of AI and data. These include the AI Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689), the General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679), the Data Act (Regulation (EU) 2023/2854) and Data Governance Act (Regulation (EU) 2022/868), the Digital Services Act (Regulation (EU) 2022/2065), the Network and Information Security Directive (Directive (EU) 2022/2555), the Digital Operational Resilience Act (Regulation (EU) 2022/2554), and the Cyber Resilience Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/2847). Each of these instruments addresses a distinct but overlapping set of concerns: the safety and trustworthiness of AI systems, the protection of personal data and fundamental rights, the resilience of critical digital infrastructures, the governance of data flows, and the cybersecurity of connected products. Taken together, they impose on organizations a set of compliance obligations that share a common analytical thread: the identification, assessment, and management of risk.

Risk management is a central concern in this regulatory landscape. The AI Act requires providers of high-risk AI systems to establish, implement, document, and maintain a risk management system as a continuous and iterative process throughout the system lifecycle. The GDPR requires controllers to implement security measures appropriate to the risk and, in high-risk processing situations, to carry out a data protection impact assessment. NIS2 and DORA impose risk management frameworks on essential entities and financial institutions respectively. The Cyber Resilience Act requires manufacturers to assess and address cybersecurity risks associated with products with digital elements. Across all these instruments, risk management is simultaneously a process obligation, a documentation obligation, and, in many cases, a governance obligation that must be embedded within the organization's management systems and accountability structures.

At the same time, a body of technical standards has developed to support organizations in meeting these obligations. ISO 31000:2018 (International Organization for Standardization, 2018) provides the foundational risk management architecture. ISO/IEC 23894:2023 (International Organization for Standardization, 2023a) extends that architecture specifically for AI systems. IEC 31010:2019 (International Organization for Standardization, 2019) catalogues the techniques available for executing risk assessment activities. ISO/IEC 42001:2023 (International Organization for Standardization, 2023b) embeds AI risk management within a broader AI management system framework. ISO/IEC 42005:2025 (International Organization for Standardization, 2025) specifies a structured process for AI system impact assessment. These standards do not map straightforwardly onto regulatory requirements: they address different aspects of the risk management problem,

operate at different levels of abstraction, and are sometimes rooted in different conceptual traditions. The standards community and the regulatory community have developed partially overlapping but non-identical vocabularies for risk, and the relationships between them require careful analysis.

HARNES (*Harnessing AI and Data-Intensive Technologies*) is a research network funded under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie programme (grant agreement No 101169409), running from January 2025 to December 2028. The network brings together doctoral candidates and supervisors across European academic and research institutions to advance the state of the art in the governance, compliance, and technical management of AI and data-intensive systems. Work Package 2 of HARNES is specifically concerned with the development of models and tools to support risk assessment and management in the context of EU AI and data regulation. This deliverable, D2.4, presents the first version of those models.

This deliverable relates to other deliverables in the HARNES project as follows. First, it builds on deliverable 2.2 (Lecat et al., 2026), a survey of methods and tools for compliance with European AI and data regulation, by taking into account its findings on semantic technologies (especially in sections 4.5 and 4.6 of that document), and applying them to create a novel semantic artefact, namely the application profile developed in section 5 of this document. There will be a second version of the deliverable at hand (deliverable 2.5), which will be a direct continuation of the work done in this deliverable, expanding it by developing application profiles for other regulatory provisions (such as GDPR), as well as providing applications to case studies. Furthermore, this deliverable will potentially inform the tools for governance of data and AI services developed in deliverable 2.3, as well as the impact assessments and domain-specific analyses that will be introduced in deliverables 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3 of work package 3 of this project.

1.2 Motivation

Risk assessment occupies a special position in the governance of AI and data-intensive technologies. It is mandated by regulation, structured by technical standards, and expected to produce documented outputs that serve as compliance artefacts - yet, the conceptual and semantic infrastructure required to connect these three layers remains underdeveloped. Organizations subject to the AI Act, the GDPR, or adjacent instruments cannot simply adopt a single standard and expect its vocabulary to satisfy their regulatory obligations. Nor can they read the regulatory text in isolation and derive from it a complete, operationalizable risk management process. The connection between legal requirement and operational practice must be constructed, and constructing it requires a shared representational foundation.

This gap has practical consequences. Providers of high-risk AI systems must document a risk management system in a form that is both internally coherent and externally verifiable by notified

bodies or market surveillance authorities. Deployers subject to the fundamental rights impact assessment obligation under Article 27 of the AI Act must produce a documentary artefact whose scope, content, and relationship to the underlying risk analysis are not fully specified by the regulation itself. Controllers carrying out data protection impact assessments under GDPR Article 35 must situate that assessment within a broader organizational risk management practice. In each of these situations, organizations face a translation problem: how to move from legal requirements to documented processes, and from documented processes to machine-readable, interoperable representations that can support audit and compliance.

A further motivation concerns the role of semantic technologies in addressing this challenge. Semantic models (expressed in RDF, OWL, SKOS, and related formats) offer a means of representing the concepts, relationships, and constraints that constitute the risk management domain in a way that is machine-readable, interoperable across tools and contexts, and extensible to new regulatory requirements as they emerge. The use of SHACL shapes allows documentation requirements to be encoded as validation constraints, enabling automated completeness checking against regulatory and standards-based criteria. The Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV) and its associated modules, including DPV/RISK, have demonstrated that this approach is viable for data protection governance. The question motivating this deliverable is whether a comparable semantic infrastructure can be developed for AI risk management under the AI Act, and how it can be integrated with the data protection and cybersecurity governance vocabularies that adjacent regulations require.

The motivation for this deliverable is therefore twofold: first, there is a practical need for clarity about what risk management in the context of EU AI and data regulation actually requires, at the level of both legal obligation and operational process. Second, there is a research and infrastructure need for reusable, interoperable models that practitioners and researchers working in this space can use as a common foundation, rather than developing isolated and incompatible solutions to the same underlying problem. This deliverable addresses both by establishing the theoretical foundations, evaluating candidate semantic models, and developing an application profile grounded in the requirements of the AI Act.

1.3 Contributions

This deliverable aims to answer the following research question: “How can the risk assessment and mitigation requirement in AI Act Art. 9 be modelled using semantic web technologies to support automated compliance checking?”

To this end, this deliverable makes three interconnected contributions to the governance of risk assessment and management in the context of EU AI and data regulation.

The first is a systematic conceptual analysis of risk across the relevant ISO and IEC standards and EU regulatory instruments, presented in Section 3. This analysis identifies two broad definitional traditions: a *deviation-from-objectives* tradition associated with ISO 31000 and ISO/IEC 23894, and a *harm-oriented* tradition associated with the AI Act, GDPR, and adjacent EU regulations. It further maps the standards architecture against the regulatory landscape. It also distinguishes risk assessment from impact assessment as related but non-identical objects. This analysis serves as the conceptual foundation for the rest of the deliverable.

The second is a structured comparative evaluation of eleven existing semantic risk management models against six explicit criteria, presented in Section 4. On the basis of this evaluation, DPV/RISK is selected as the primary semantic foundation for the application profile. Explicit justifications are provided for each selection decision.

The third is an application profile operationalizing the risk management requirements of the AI Act in machine-readable, validatable form, presented in Section 4. This profile traces atomic requirements from Article 9 of the AI Act through their corresponding operationalizations in ISO 31000 and ISO/IEC 23894, translates them into DPV/RISK concepts, identifies gaps requiring new concepts, and encodes documentation obligations as SHACL shapes enabling automated completeness checking.

Regulatory Scope

The primary regulatory instrument addressed in this deliverable is the EU AI Act, with a focus on the risk management obligations for providers of high-risk AI systems under Article 9. The AI Act is the primary focus for two reasons. First, it is the most procedurally elaborated of the EU instruments in its risk management requirements: Article 9 specifies not only that a risk management system must exist, but structures the system as a continuous, iterative, lifecycle-spanning process with identifiable phases that allow mapping onto the ISO risk management architecture. This makes it the most tractable starting point for the development of application profiles that connect legal requirements to semantic representations. Second, as the instrument that most directly and comprehensively governs AI systems as such, it is the natural anchor for a deliverable whose subject matter is risk management in AI and data-intensive contexts.

Other instruments in the EU landscape, including the GDPR, DSA, NIS2, DORA, and the Cyber Resilience Act, are addressed in the theoretical foundations of Section 3, where they are mapped against the standards architecture and characterized in terms of their affected subjects, obligated actors, and required outputs. Dedicated application profiles for these instruments are considered for subsequent versions of this deliverable. The conceptual framework and semantic foundation established here are designed to accommodate them without requiring structural revision.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable

The remainder of this deliverable is organized as follows.

Section 2 establishes the theoretical foundations. It clarifies the concept of risk as it appears across the relevant standards and regulatory instruments, describes the layered architecture of ISO 31000, ISO/IEC 23894, IEC 31010, ISO/IEC 42001, and ISO/IEC 42005, maps EU regulatory requirements against that architecture, distinguishes risk assessment from impact assessment, and situates the NIST AI RMF and adjacent governance frameworks within the overall landscape.

Section 3 evaluates candidate semantic risk management models. It examines eleven models across the four ISO-style risk management phases of identification, analysis, evaluation, and treatment, consolidates the comparison in a set of structured tables, and selects DPV/RISK as the primary semantic foundation with AIRO and VAIR as AI-specific complements.

Section 4 develops the application profile. It extracts atomic requirements from Article 9 of the AI Act, maps each requirement to its operationalization in ISO 31000 and ISO/IEC 23894, translates the result into DPV/RISK concepts, identifies gaps requiring new concept proposals, and encodes the resulting documentation obligations as SHACL shapes for automated compliance checking.

Section 5 concludes the deliverable. It reflects on risks that fall beyond the scope of current regulations and standards, and identifies directions for future work.

2 THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS: RISK IN AI AND DATA

This section establishes the conceptual foundation for the risk management model developed later in the deliverable. It clarifies the concept of risk, describes the risk management architecture offered by the relevant ISO and IEC standards, maps EU regulatory requirements against that architecture, and distinguishes risk assessment from impact assessment as related, but non-identical assessments.

The section is descriptive rather than normative. Its purpose is not to argue that one standard or regulation is preferable to another, but to make the landscape legible. The central analytical thread is the question of the affected subject: whose objectives, interests, rights, safety, security, or social conditions are affected by the risk? This question matters because the standards and regulations do not always locate risk in the same place. In some standards, risk is primarily linked to organizational objectives. In many EU regulations, risk is linked to protected persons, protected interests, systems, services, markets, or society.

The five standards considered in this section play different roles. ISO 31000 provides the general risk management architecture. ISO/IEC 23894 extends that architecture for AI systems and is intended to be used together with ISO 31000. IEC 31010 provides a catalogue of techniques for carrying out risk assessment activities. ISO/IEC 42001 turns AI risk management into an AI management system requirement. ISO/IEC 42005 specifies a structured process for AI system impact assessment. These standards are therefore not treated as equivalent sources performing the same function. They form a layered architecture in which each standard contributes a different element.

2.1 The Concept of Risk in International Standards

The term "risk" appears across ISO 31000, ISO/IEC 23894, IEC 31010, ISO/IEC 42001, ISO/IEC 42005, the AI Act, the GDPR, the Digital Services Act, NIS2, DORA, and the Cyber Resilience Act. However, these instruments do not use the term in a single shared sense. In some instruments, risk is defined broadly as the effect of uncertainty on objectives. In others, risk is used mainly in a harm-oriented way, referring to adverse effects on protected interests such as health, safety, fundamental rights, data protection, cybersecurity, operational continuity, or societal resilience.

This divergence is not imposed from outside the standards. ISO/IEC 23894 acknowledges that risk can be understood differently across international standards, with some approaches treating risk as deviation from objectives and others treating risk as the possibility of harm or negative outcomes. ISO/IEC 42001 also recognizes that the way an organization defines and approaches risk can vary across sectors and industries, and that the organization must adopt a view of risk suited to its context.

For the purposes of this deliverable, two broad traditions are distinguished. This is an analytical distinction adopted for this deliverable rather than a settled taxonomy in the literature, where risk

definitions are usually catalogued in finer-grained typologies (Aven, 2012). It parallels, however, two established contrasts. The first is the classical risk-management distinction between speculative risks, which admit both gain and loss, and pure risks, which admit only loss (Vaughan & Vaughan, 2008). The second is the coexistence within ISO's own vocabulary of an objectives-based definition of risk (ISO 31000:2018) and a harm-based definition (ISO/IEC Guide 51:2014 (International Organization for Standardization, 2014)); the objectives-based definition was itself deliberately adopted as a departure from earlier event- and harm-centred definitions. The first tradition distinguished here is the deviation-from-objectives tradition. In this tradition, risk can include positive and negative effects because it is defined in relation to objectives and uncertainty. ISO 31000 and ISO/IEC 23894 primarily belong to this tradition. ISO/IEC 42001 also partly belongs to it because it frames AI risk assessment in relation to AI objectives and the organization's AI management system. The second is the harm-oriented tradition. In this tradition, risk is framed mainly as the possibility of negative consequences for protected interests. The AI Act, GDPR, DSA, NIS2, DORA, and the Cyber Resilience Act largely operate in this second tradition, although not all of them do so in the same way (Gellert, 2021).

This division is an analytical generalization rather than a perfect taxonomy. The DSA's concept of systemic risk, for example, has features of both traditions because it is concerned with large-scale social effects as well as legally protected interests. ISO/IEC 42001 and ISO/IEC 42005 also bridge the traditions by connecting organizational risk management with impacts on individuals, groups, and societies. Nevertheless, the distinction is useful because it explains why the same term, "risk," can produce different assessment objects and compliance duties depending on the instrument being applied.

This deliverable adopts ISO 31000's vocabulary as a working analytical vocabulary. The relevant elements are *risk source*, *event*, *consequence*, and *likelihood*. A *risk source* is the origin or condition from which risk may arise. An *event* is an occurrence or change of circumstances. A *consequence* is the effect that follows from the event. *Likelihood* expresses how probable or plausible the event or consequence is within the assessment context. These concepts are not treated as a neutral definition of all regulatory risk; they are used because ISO 31000 provides the general vocabulary that ISO/IEC 23894 extends for AI systems.

A fifth analytical element is added: the affected subject. This is not an ISO 31000 primitive. It is introduced here because both the AI-specific standards and the EU regulations make it necessary to ask who or what bears the consequence of risk. ISO/IEC 23894 requires organizations to identify consequences not only for the organization itself, but also for individuals, communities, groups, and societies. It also recognizes that consequences can be positive or negative and that the groups benefiting from an AI system may differ from the groups experiencing negative consequences.

The affected-subject question is therefore the thread that runs through the rest of this section. ISO 31000 begins from the organization and its objectives, with stakeholders entering through context analysis, consultation, and consequence assessment. EU regulatory instruments more often begin from the protected subject: the data subject, end user, affected person, critical service, financial system, or society.

Table 2.1 - Two definitional traditions of risk

	Deviation-from-objectives tradition	Harm-oriented tradition
Orientation of risk	Risk can involve positive or negative deviation from objectives.	Risk is mainly framed as the possibility of negative outcomes or harm.
Reference point	Organizational objectives, decision-making, uncertainty, value creation, and value protection.	Protected legal interests, such as health, safety, fundamental rights, personal data, cybersecurity, continuity, and resilience.
Primary affected subject	The organization is the starting point, although stakeholders can enter through context, consultation, and consequence analysis.	Third parties are central, such as data subjects, end users, affected persons, service users, markets, or society.
Purpose of risk management	Risk management supports informed decision-making and the achievement of objectives.	Risk management supports protection of legally defined interests and demonstration of compliance.
Treatment of impact	Impact is generally treated through consequence analysis within risk assessment.	Impact may become a legally triggered assessment or documentation obligation, such as a DPIA or FRIA.
Main instruments	ISO 31000; ISO/IEC 23894; ISO/IEC 42001 in part	AI Act; GDPR; DSA; NIS2; DORA; Cyber Resilience Act

2.2 Risk Management in the Standards

The standards under review collectively provide an integrated architecture for risk management in AI and data contexts. ISO 31000 provides the general architecture. ISO/IEC 23894 extends that architecture for AI. IEC 31010 provides techniques for carrying out risk assessment activities. ISO/IEC 42001 embeds the AI risk management process into a wider AI management system. ISO/IEC 42005 provides a dedicated process for AI system impact assessment. These standards are therefore not peers performing the same role; instead, they form a layered structure in which each standard contributes a different part of the overall picture.

Beyond the ISO standards examined here, it is relevant to mention that European Committee for Standardisation (CEN) and European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation (CENELEC) have been requested to create harmonised standards for various key areas of the AI Act, including risk management. As of June 2026, work on this harmonised standard has not yet concluded; even after completion, approval from the European Commission could delay its publication by several months, and the development process is further complicated by a lawsuit filed by ISO/IEC in the Court of Justice of the European Union in December 2024, aiming to ensure the respect of its

copyrights (Kilian et al., 2025). European harmonised standards are therefore not considered in the present analysis.

ISO 31000: General risk management

ISO 31000 is the baseline for risk management. It organizes risk management around three layers: principles, framework, and process. The principles layer expresses the normative commitments of risk management. These include integration into organizational activities, a structured and comprehensive approach, customization to context, stakeholder inclusiveness, dynamism, reliance on the best available information, attention to human and cultural factors, and continual improvement. These principles do not themselves constitute a risk assessment. Rather, they guide how the organization designs and operates the framework and process.

The framework layer is the governance layer. It concerns the integration of risk management into the organization through leadership and commitment, design, implementation, evaluation, and improvement. This layer is important because risk management is not treated as a one-off analytical exercise, but is instead embedded in organizational responsibilities, resources, decision-making structures, communication practices, and review mechanisms.

The process layer is the operational loop. It includes establishing the scope, context, and criteria; assessing risk; treating risk; monitoring and reviewing; and recording and reporting. Communication and consultation cut across the process. Within this process, risk assessment consists of identification, analysis, and evaluation. Identification concerns what could happen and what sources of uncertainty are relevant. Analysis concerns the nature and level of risk, including consequences, likelihood, controls, uncertainty, and assumptions. Evaluation compares the results of the analysis against risk criteria and supports decisions about whether treatment is needed. Treatment then concerns the selection and implementation of measures to address the risk.

IEC 31010: Techniques for risk assessment

IEC 31010 plays a different role from ISO 31000. It is not a risk management framework, but a techniques standard for risk assessment. It supports activities such as eliciting views from stakeholders and experts, identifying risk, determining sources, causes and drivers of risk, analysing controls, understanding consequences and likelihood, analysing dependencies and interactions, providing measures of risk, evaluating the significance of risk, selecting between options, and recording and reporting.

This distinction between process and technique is important. The same risk management process can be executed through different techniques. Risk identification can be supported by interviews, checklists, taxonomies, scenario analysis, or structured workshops. Risk analysis can be supported by consequence/likelihood matrices, bow-tie analysis, Bayesian networks, event trees, fault trees,

or simulation. Risk evaluation and treatment selection can be supported by risk indices, ALARP-style reasoning, cost-benefit analysis, or multi-criteria analysis. A semantic model should therefore represent the activity being performed separately from the technique used to perform it.

ISO/IEC 23894: AI risk management

ISO/IEC 23894 extends the ISO 31000 architecture for AI systems. It is intended to be used in connection with ISO 31000 and follows the same broad structure: principles, framework, and process. The purpose is not to replace ISO 31000, but to add AI-specific guidance where the general framework requires specialization. ISO/IEC 42005 Annex B also describes ISO/IEC 23894 as being based on ISO 31000 and explains that ISO/IEC 23894 applies ISO 31000's principles, framework, and processes in the AI context.

At the principles layer, ISO/IEC 23894 adds AI-specific implications to general risk management principles. It highlights the dynamic character of AI systems, the importance of stakeholder inclusion, the limits of available information, the need to consider human and cultural factors, and the importance of continual improvement. These additions matter because AI systems can change over time, operate in complex socio-technical settings, and affect individuals and societies in ways that are not always visible at design time.

At the framework layer, ISO/IEC 23894 adds AI-specific context. Organizations are expected to understand their role in relation to AI systems, the legal and regulatory environment, the expectations of stakeholders, the technical and organizational dependencies surrounding the system, and the lifecycle stage at which the system is being assessed. This lifecycle orientation is important because AI risk management is not limited to pre-deployment assessment. It can continue through deployment, operation, monitoring, re-evaluation, and retirement or replacement.

At the process layer, ISO/IEC 23894 provides AI-specific detail for risk assessment and risk treatment. As in ISO 31000, risk assessment includes risk identification, risk analysis, and risk evaluation. In the AI context, risk identification includes identifying assets and their value, risk sources, potential events and outcomes, existing controls, and consequences. The standard also requires attention to consequences for the organization, individuals, communities, groups, and societies. It specifically notes that organizations should identify differences between groups that benefit from the technology and groups that experience negative consequences.

Risk analysis in ISO/IEC 23894 includes assessment of consequences and likelihood. The standard distinguishes between business impact analysis, impact analysis for individuals, and societal impact analysis. Business impact analysis concerns the degree to which the organization is affected. Impact analysis for individuals concerns the degree to which individuals may be affected by the development or use of AI, including impacts connected to data, bias, fundamental rights, fairness, safety, and cultural or jurisdictional context. Societal impact analysis concerns the degree to which

societies may be affected, including the reach of the AI system and its effects on social or cultural values.

Risk evaluation compares analysed risks with the risk criteria established earlier in the risk management process. Risk treatment then concerns the selection of risk treatment options, such as removing the risk source, changing likelihood, changing consequences, sharing risk, or retaining risk by informed decision. ISO/IEC 23894 also addresses the preparation and implementation of risk treatment plans, verification of treatment effectiveness, monitoring and review, and recording and reporting. The risk management record should allow traceability of each identified risk through the risk management process.

ISO/IEC 23894 also contributes two catalogues that are important for semantic modelling. Annex A identifies AI-related objectives that can be considered when identifying risks, including accountability, AI expertise, data quality, environmental impact, fairness, maintainability, privacy, robustness, safety, security, transparency, and explainability. Annex B identifies AI-related risk sources, including complexity of environment, lack of transparency and explainability, level of automation, risk sources related to machine learning, system hardware issues, system lifecycle issues, and technology readiness. These catalogues are not exhaustive, but they provide useful structure for representing AI-specific risks.

ISO/IEC 42001: AI management system

ISO/IEC 42001 adds the management-system layer. It specifies requirements for establishing, implementing, maintaining, and continually improving an AI management system. It includes requirements on organizational context, leadership, planning, support, operation, performance evaluation, and improvement. Within this management system, AI risk assessment, AI risk treatment, and AI system impact assessment are treated as organizational processes that must be defined, documented, maintained, and reviewed.

In relation to AI risk assessment, ISO/IEC 42001 requires the organization to define a process that is informed by and aligned with AI policy and AI objectives. The process must be capable of producing consistent, valid, and comparable results. It identifies risks that aid or prevent achievement of AI objectives, analyses consequences for the organization, individuals, and societies, assesses likelihood where applicable, determines risk levels, compares results with risk criteria, and prioritizes risks for treatment. The organization must retain documented information about the AI risk assessment process.

In relation to AI risk treatment, ISO/IEC 42001 requires the organization to select appropriate treatment options, determine necessary controls, and compare them with the controls catalogued in Annex A of the standard. Annex A of ISO/IEC 42001 catalogues AI-specific controls covering policies, internal organization, resources, impact assessment, lifecycle, data, information for interested parties, use of AI systems, and third-party relationships. Where Annex A does not adequately address an identified risk, the organization must identify additional controls. The

organization must also produce a statement of applicability that documents the necessary controls and justifies their inclusion or exclusion. It must formulate an AI risk treatment plan, obtain approval for that plan and for acceptance of residual AI risks, and retain documented information about the treatment process.

ISO/IEC 42001 is especially relevant to EU regulatory obligations that require organizational documentation, accountability, controls, and management-system evidence. In the AI Act context, it is the closest standards-side analogue to Article 17 on quality management systems, while ISO/IEC 23894 is closer to Article 9's risk management process.

ISO/IEC 42005: AI system impact assessment

ISO/IEC 42005 adds a dedicated AI system impact assessment process. This is important because impact assessment is not only a regulatory concept. ISO/IEC 42005 treats AI system impact assessment as a structured process that can be integrated with organizational management processes, including organizational risk assessment and other types of impact assessment. It addresses documenting the process, timing, scope, allocation of responsibilities, thresholds for sensitive uses and restricted uses, performance of the assessment, analysis of results, recording and reporting, approval, monitoring, and review.

ISO/IEC 42005 also contributes a detailed documentation structure. It includes AI system description, functionalities and capabilities, system purpose, intended uses, unintended uses, data information and data quality, algorithm and model information, deployment environment, relevant interested parties, and actual and reasonably foreseeable impacts. It also covers AI system failures and reasonably foreseeable misuse, and recommends documenting measures to address harms and benefits.

Annex B of ISO/IEC 42005 is particularly important for this deliverable because it explains the relationship between AI system impact assessment and AI risk management, which will be elaborated in section 2.4. It distinguishes risk management as an overall organizational activity from AI system impact assessment as a more product- or service-oriented process focused on reasonably foreseeable impacts of AI systems on individuals, groups of individuals, societies, and the environment. It also states that AI system impact assessments are an important part of the overall risk management lifecycle and an input to risk assessment.

The standards and adjacent frameworks therefore form a layered architecture. ISO 31000 provides the conceptual baseline. ISO/IEC 23894 specializes it for AI. IEC 31010 supplies techniques for executing assessment work. ISO/IEC 42001 turns AI risk management into a management-system requirement. ISO/IEC 42005 specifies AI system impact assessment as a structured process with its own documentation and lifecycle. The NIST AI RMF provides a complementary operational framework organized around governance, mapping, measurement, and management of AI risks. UNESCO and OECD add broader ethics, human-rights, and policy-oriented vocabularies. This

architecture provides the reference point for the next subsection, which examines which parts of it are adopted, modified, or left unspecified by EU regulation.

Table 2.2 - Comparison of the five standards

Standard	Primary role	Unit of analysis	Key concepts contributed	Relevance to AI Act compliance
ISO 31000	General risk management baseline	Organization, activity, decision, project, process, or system	Principles, framework, process; risk source, event, consequence, likelihood; risk assessment and risk treatment distinction	Provides the conceptual baseline for continuous and iterative risk management.
ISO/IEC 23894	AI-specific extension of ISO 31000	AI system in organizational and lifecycle context	AI-specific risk sources; AI-related objectives; business, individual, and societal impact analysis; lifecycle alignment	Directly informs the logic of AI Act Article 9 on risk management systems.
IEC 31010	Risk assessment techniques catalogue	Assessment activity or method	Techniques for risk identification, analysis, evaluation, option selection, recording, and reporting	Supports execution of AI Act Article 9, but does not itself define legal compliance.
ISO/IEC 42001	AI management system requirements	Organization-level AI management system	AI risk assessment; AI risk treatment; AI system impact assessment; controls; statement of applicability; documented information	Closest standards-side analogue to AI Act Article 17 on quality management systems.
ISO/IEC 42005	AI system impact assessment process	AI system	Structured impact assessment process; scope, timing, responsibilities, thresholds, documentation, approval, monitoring, and review	Closest standards-side analogue to AI Act Article 27 FRIA, although not legally identical.

2.3 Risk Management Requirements in EU AI and Data Regulation

EU regulations mandate risk management in multiple ways, but they do not adopt the standards architecture uniformly. The relevant instruments address different layers of the standards architecture: some impose process obligations, some impose framework obligations, some require management-system documentation, and others create legally triggered impact-assessment artefacts. They also differ in who is obligated and who is affected.

The regulations can be grouped by dominant affected-subject category. The first group is the product-safety lineage, which includes the AI Act and the Cyber Resilience Act. In this lineage, the affected subjects are end users, persons exposed to the product or system, and third parties who may be harmed by its operation. The protected interests are health, safety, cybersecurity, and, in the case of the AI Act, fundamental rights. The compliance mechanisms include risk management systems, technical documentation, quality management systems, conformity assessment, and post-market monitoring.

The second group is the data-protection lineage, centred on the GDPR. Here, the affected subject is the data subject. Risk is framed as risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons. The relevant obligations include data protection by design and by default, risk-appropriate technical and organizational security measures, and the data protection impact assessment for processing likely to result in high risk.

The third group is the systemic and operational lineage, which includes NIS2, DORA, and DSA. In this lineage, the affected subject may be the network and information system, the continuity of a critical service, financial stability, or society as a whole. Risk is framed around cybersecurity, operational resilience, systemic effects, and the functioning of digital or financial infrastructures.

For a more in-depth analysis of the regulatory framework governing AI and data, taking into account specific actors, roles, objectives, and their relevance to technologies with special emphasis on the interrelations between AI regulation and GDPR, please refer to deliverable 1.1 of this project (*"Creating an Atlas of AI and Data Regulatory Frameworks"*)¹.

AI Act

Article 9 in the AI Act is the core risk management provision. It requires a risk management system for high-risk AI systems and frames that system as a continuous and iterative process throughout the lifecycle. Article 9(2) structures the system around four main steps: identification and analysis of known and reasonably foreseeable risks to health, safety, or fundamental rights when the system is used according to its intended purpose; estimation and evaluation of risks that may emerge under intended use and reasonably foreseeable misuse; evaluation of risks based on data gathered from the post-market monitoring system referred to in Article 72; and adoption of appropriate and targeted risk management measures. The post-market monitoring system itself is established under Article 72; Article 9(2)(c) refers to it as an input to ongoing risk evaluation. This structure is close to the ISO 31000 process layer and to ISO/IEC 23894's AI-specific lifecycle logic, even though the AI Act remains harm-oriented because the relevant risks are risks to health, safety, and fundamental rights.

Article 10 is related to but distinct from the risk management obligation, because it concerns data and data governance. It does not establish a complete risk management process by itself, but it addresses an important class of AI risk sources: training, validation, and testing data; data quality;

¹At the time of writing, this deliverable is still work in progress and due at the same time as the deliverable at hand (June 2026). Therefore, it is not properly cited.

representativeness; bias; and governance. This maps closely to ISO/IEC 23894's treatment of data as a risk source and to ISO/IEC 42001's emphasis on data quality and trustworthiness concerns.

Article 17 operates at the framework or management-system layer. It requires a quality management system and therefore resembles the management-system logic of ISO/IEC 42001 more than the assessment-process logic of ISO 31000 alone. Article 17 is important because it connects risk management to organizational governance, documentation, responsibility, repeatability, and control.

Article 27 introduces the fundamental rights impact assessment. This is best understood as a legally triggered impact-assessment artefact. It overlaps conceptually with ISO/IEC 42005 because both concern the assessment of impacts of AI systems on individuals and societies. However, the relationship is not one of equivalence. ISO/IEC 42005 specifies a standards-based AI system impact assessment process, while Article 27 creates a legal obligation for specified deployers and defines a regulatory compliance artefact. Forthcoming deliverables 3.3 (due June 2026), 3.4 and 3.5 (both due December 2027) of this project will provide a deeper investigation into impacts on fundamental rights.

GDPR

The GDPR uses risk primarily in a harm-oriented and data-subject-centred way. Articles 24 and 25 impose framework-layer obligations on controllers, including appropriate technical and organizational measures and data protection by design and by default. Article 32 combines framework and process logic by requiring security measures appropriate to the risk. Article 32(2) specifically requires attention to the risks presented by processing, including accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorized disclosure of, or access to personal data that are transmitted, stored, or otherwise processed.

Article 35 requires the data protection impact assessment. The DPIA is a legally triggered impact-assessment instrument focused on processing likely to result in high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons. It produces a documentary artefact that is distinct from, although related to, the underlying risk assessment work. Article 36 adds the possibility of prior consultation with the supervisory authority where the controller cannot sufficiently mitigate the risk.

Digital Services Act

The DSA uses risk in a systemic sense. Article 34 requires providers of very large online platforms and very large online search engines to identify, analyse, and assess systemic risks in the Union that stem from the design or functioning of their services and related systems, including algorithmic systems, or from the use made of their services. The article specifies four categories of systemic risk that must be assessed: the dissemination of illegal content through the service; effects on the exercise of fundamental rights; effects on civic discourse, electoral processes, and public security;

and effects in relation to gender-based violence, the protection of public health and minors, and serious negative consequences to physical and mental well-being. The assessment must also consider how the design, functioning, and use of specific systems contribute to those risks, including content moderation systems, recommender systems, advertising systems, data-related practices, and intentional manipulation. The affected subject is therefore broader than an individual user. It includes users, groups, public discourse, fundamental rights, public health, electoral processes, public security, and society more generally.

Compared with the standards architecture, the DSA specifies risk categories and contributing factors in regulatory terms, but does not import the ISO architecture of principles, framework, process, technique selection, and treatment planning. The internal analytical process by which the assessment is to be performed is therefore largely left to the obligated entity, within the boundaries set by the regulatory specification.

NIS2 Directive

NIS2 belongs to the systemic and operational lineage. Article 21 requires cybersecurity risk-management measures for essential and important entities. These obligations are framework-heavy because they require entities to adopt appropriate and proportionate technical, operational, and organizational measures to manage risks posed to the security of network and information systems.

NIS2 also contains a structurally distinct risk-assessment instrument. Article 22 allows the Cooperation Group, in cooperation with the Commission and ENISA, to carry out coordinated security risk assessments of specific critical ICT services, ICT systems, or ICT product supply chains, taking into account technical and, where relevant, non-technical risk factors. This is not the same activity as the entity-level risk management required by Article 21. It is a coordinated, EU-level, supply-chain-oriented assessment carried out by EU institutions and bodies rather than by individual obligated entities. It therefore represents a different kind of risk assessment instrument altogether, one that operates above the level of the individual organization.

Digital Operational Resilience Act

DORA belongs to the systemic and operational lineage but is specific to the financial sector. Its centre of gravity is the ICT risk management framework. DORA requires financial entities to identify, classify, and manage ICT risk as part of digital operational resilience. Its affected subject is not only the individual user or customer, but also the continuity of ICT-supported business functions and, indirectly, financial stability.

DORA contains specific risk assessment triggers. Article 8(3) requires financial entities, other than microenterprises, to perform a risk assessment upon each major change in network and information system infrastructure, processes, or procedures affecting ICT-supported business functions, information assets, or ICT assets. Article 8(7) requires financial entities, other than microenterprises,

to conduct a specific ICT risk assessment on all legacy ICT systems at least yearly and, in any case, before and after connecting technologies, applications, or systems. These provisions show a more event-triggered and periodic model of risk assessment than the AI Act's lifecycle formulation.

Cyber Resilience Act

The Cyber Resilience Act follows the product-safety lineage. It concerns products with digital elements and requires manufacturers to assess and address cybersecurity risks associated with those products. Article 13(2) requires manufacturers to undertake an assessment of the cybersecurity risks associated with a product with digital elements and to take the outcome of that assessment into account during the planning, design, development, production, delivery, and maintenance phases. The substantive cybersecurity requirements that the assessment must address are specified in Annex I of the CRA.

The CRA therefore links cybersecurity risk assessment to product compliance, technical documentation, and conformity obligations. Its affected subjects are users and third parties exposed to vulnerabilities in products with digital elements. Its logic is closer to product conformity and technical documentation than to the full risk management architecture of ISO 31000.

The regulatory picture is therefore fragmented. EU instruments mandate different parts of the standards architecture. The principles layer is usually assumed rather than expressly specified. Framework and process obligations appear unevenly. Documentary outputs are often specified more clearly than the analytical methods that produce them. The affected subject also changes across instruments: the user, the data subject, the affected person, the organization, the service, the market, or society. This is the practical problem the semantic model must address.

Table 2.3a - Product-safety lineage: regulation against standards architecture

Regulatory provision	Standards layer(s) addressed	Required output	Obligated subject	Affected subject
AI Act Art. 9	Process	Risk management system documentation; continuous lifecycle process	Provider	Health, safety, and fundamental rights of affected persons
AI Act Art. 10	Process / data governance	Data and data governance documentation	Provider	Persons whose data is processed or who are affected by system outputs

AI Act Art. 17	Framework / management system	Quality management system documentation	Provider	Primarily organizational; indirectly affected persons
AI Act Art. 27	Impact assessment	Fundamental rights impact assessment documentation and related notification where required	Deployer, for specified high-risk AI systems	Persons and groups affected in their fundamental rights
Cyber Resilience Act Art. 13(2) and Annex I	Process / management system	Cybersecurity risk assessment and technical documentation	Manufacturer	Users and third parties exposed to products with digital elements

Table 2.3b - Data-protection lineage: regulation against standards architecture

Regulatory provision	Standards layer(s) addressed	Required output	Obligated subject	Affected subject
GDPR Arts. 24 / 25	Framework	Technical and organizational measures; data protection by design and by default	Controller	Data subjects
GDPR Art. 32	Framework / process	Risk-appropriate security measures	Controller and processor	Data subjects
GDPR Art. 35	Impact assessment	Data protection impact assessment documentation; prior consultation where required	Controller	Data subjects

Table 2.3c - Systemic and operational lineage: regulation against standards architecture

Regulatory provision	Standards layer(s) addressed	Required output	Obligated subject	Affected subject
DSA Art. 34	Process, limited	Systemic risk assessment	Provider of very large online	Society, users, fundamental

		covering four statutory categories	platform or very large online search engine	rights, public health, civic discourse, electoral processes, and public security
NIS2 Art. 21	Framework / process	Cybersecurity risk management measures	Essential and important entities	Network and information systems; users and services dependent on them
NIS2 Art. 22	Coordinated supply-chain risk assessment	Coordinated security risk assessment of critical ICT services, ICT systems, or ICT product supply chains	Cooperation Group, Commission, and ENISA	Critical ICT supply chains; dependent entities and services
DORA Arts. 5–16, especially Art. 8	Framework / process	ICT risk management framework; major-change risk assessments; yearly legacy ICT risk assessments	Financial entities	Operational resilience and financial stability

Table 2.3d - Summary view: layer coverage across regulations

Regulation	Principles	Framework	Process	Technique	Management system	Impact assessment
AI Act	-	●	●	-	●	●
GDPR	-	●	●	-	-	●
DSA	-	-	●	-	-	-
NIS2	-	●	●	-	-	-
DORA	-	●	●	-	●	-

CRA	-	-	●	-	●	-
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Legend: ● indicates that the regulation contains obligations addressing that layer of the standards architecture; - indicates that the layer is assumed, left unspecified, or not addressed.

2.4 Impact Assessments versus Risk Assessments

The preceding subsections introduced several assessment objects: risk assessment in the ISO sense, business and societal impact analysis in ISO/IEC 23894, AI system impact assessment in ISO/IEC 42005, DPIA under the GDPR, and FRIA under the AI Act. These objects are related, but they are not identical. This subsection clarifies their relationship.

Risk assessment, in the ISO sense, is an analytical component of risk management. It consists of identification, analysis, and evaluation. It is not necessarily a standalone document, although it can produce documented outputs. Its function is to support decisions about risk treatment. In ISO/IEC 23894, this risk assessment logic is extended to AI systems and includes analysis of consequences for the organization, individuals, and societies.

Impact analysis appears inside this risk assessment structure. ISO/IEC 23894 distinguishes business impact analysis, impact analysis for individuals, and societal impact analysis as part of consequence assessment. From this perspective, impact analysis is nested within risk analysis. It is a component of the broader risk assessment process rather than a separate assessment object.

ISO/IEC 42005 addresses a different scope. It does not contradict the nested view in ISO/IEC 23894; rather, it elevates AI system impact assessment to a structured process in its own right because that is the activity it is specifically about. This process has its own timing, scope, responsibilities, documentation, approval, monitoring, and review. It is integrated with organizational management processes and can be connected with organizational risk assessment and other impact assessments. The two standards are therefore consistent with each other: whether impact assessment is nested or standalone depends on whether the activity being described is risk analysis (in which case impact analysis is one of its components) or impact assessment (in which case it is the activity itself, and has its own structure).

ISO/IEC 42005 Annex B is especially important for distinguishing risk management from AI system impact assessment. It explains that risk management addresses the organization and its activities more broadly, while AI system impact assessment focuses on reasonably foreseeable impacts of AI systems on individuals, groups of individuals, societies, and the environment in relation to potential or concrete uses of AI systems. It also states that AI system impact assessment is an important part of the risk management lifecycle and an input to successful risk assessment.

EU regulation introduces a third perspective. DPIA and FRIA are legally triggered impact-assessment artefacts. They draw on risk and impact analysis, but they are defined by legal triggers, required content, procedural timing, and potential consultation or notification obligations. They exist as compliance objects, not merely as internal analytical steps.

ISO/IEC 42001 partly bridges these perspectives. It includes AI risk assessment, AI risk treatment, and AI system impact assessment within the AI management system. It also requires the organization to consider the results of the AI system impact assessment in the AI risk assessment. This means that impact assessment can be linked both to the risk management process and to organizational governance.

The representational consequence is important. A semantic model must be able to express three relationships at once. First, impact analysis can be a component of risk analysis, as in ISO/IEC 23894. Second, AI system impact assessment can be a structured standards-based process, as in ISO/IEC 42005. Third, DPIA and FRIA can be legally triggered compliance artefacts, as in EU regulation. None of these views is wrong. They describe different aspects of overlapping governance practices.

It is therefore necessary to avoid collapsing these objects into a single undifferentiated “assessment.” Risk assessment, impact analysis, AI system impact assessment, and legally mandated impact assessment should be distinguished, while the relationships among them should also be represented.

Table 2.4 - Three assessment objects compared

Dimension	Risk assessment, ISO sense	AI system impact assessment, ISO/IEC 42005 sense	Legally mandated impact assessment, DPIA / FRIA
Trigger	Internal management need, lifecycle change, or risk management process	Organizational process, defined thresholds, sensitive use, restricted use, or reassessment triggers	Legal triggers in GDPR Art. 35 and AI Act Art. 27
Scope	Identification, analysis, and evaluation of risk	Actual and reasonably foreseeable impacts of an AI system	Statutorily specified scope
Output	Analytical input to treatment decisions	Structured assessment documentation, review, approval, monitoring, and updating	Compliance artefact, potentially notifiable or consultable with authorities
Timing	Continuous and iterative within risk management	Defined by the organizational AI system impact assessment process	Prior to processing or deployment where legally required
Obligated subject	Organization performing risk management	Organization developing, providing, or using the AI system	Controller for DPIA; deployer for FRIA

Affected subject	Organization, individuals, groups, communities, societies, depending on scope	Interested parties, individuals, groups of individuals, societies, and the environment	Data subjects for DPIA; affected persons or groups for FRIA
Procedural requirements	Internal to the management process; recorded where required	Documented process, allocation of responsibilities, review, approval, monitoring, and updating	Legal content, timing, consultation, notification, and accountability requirements
Relationship to other assessments	Can include impact analysis as part of risk analysis	Can inform and be informed by risk assessment and other impact assessments	Draws on underlying risk and impact work but has separate legal status

2.5 Adjacent AI governance frameworks

Although this deliverable adopts the ISO/IEC standards as the main standards-based reference architecture, several non-ISO frameworks and resources are relevant and are described here for completeness. They fall into three groups: an operational AI risk management framework (the NIST AI RMF), a research-based taxonomy of AI risks (the MIT AI Risk Repository), and ethics- and policy-oriented governance frameworks (the UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence and the OECD AI Principles). None of these is adopted as the primary structure, because the deliverable is organized around ISO 31000, ISO/IEC 23894, IEC 31010, ISO/IEC 42001, and ISO/IEC 42005. Each, however, contributes context, vocabulary, or empirical grounding that the ISO architecture alone does not provide.

The NIST AI RMF is a voluntary framework developed by the U.S. National Institute of Standards and Technology (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023). NIST describes it as a framework intended to help organizations better manage risks to individuals, organizations, and society associated with artificial intelligence. It is intended for voluntary use and aims to improve the ability to incorporate trustworthiness considerations into the design, development, use, and evaluation of AI products, services, and systems. The framework was released in January 2023 and is accompanied by implementation resources such as the AI RMF Playbook, Roadmap, Crosswalks, and related profiles.

The AI RMF is organized around four core functions: Govern, Map, Measure, and Manage. These functions do not reproduce the ISO 31000 sequence of risk identification, risk analysis, risk evaluation, and risk treatment. Instead, they provide an operational governance structure for AI risk management. Govern is the cross-cutting function and concerns organizational policies, accountability, roles, responsibilities, culture, legal and regulatory requirements, risk tolerance, monitoring, and review. Map concerns contextual understanding of the AI system, including its

purpose, task, deployment context, benefits, costs, assumptions, third-party components, affected individuals and groups, and potential impacts. Measure concerns testing, evaluation, verification, validation, monitoring, and measurement of AI system performance and trustworthiness. Manage concerns prioritization, response, risk treatment, residual risk, monitoring, incident response, recovery, decommissioning, and continual improvement. NIST presents these functions as the highest-level organization of AI risk management activities, with governance designed to inform and be infused throughout the other three functions.

The NIST AI RMF is also useful because it offers a compact operational vocabulary for trustworthy AI. It identifies trustworthy AI characteristics such as validity and reliability, safety, security and resilience, accountability and transparency, explainability and interpretability, privacy enhancement, and fairness with harmful bias managed. These characteristics overlap with the concerns discussed in ISO/IEC 23894 and ISO/IEC 42001, including robustness, safety, security, privacy, fairness, transparency, explainability, accountability, and human oversight. The NIST framework is therefore useful as a comparison point for checking whether a semantic model can represent the main dimensions of trustworthy AI governance.

For this deliverable, the NIST AI RMF is best treated as a complementary operational framework rather than as the primary modelling structure. It is relevant because it connects AI risk management to governance, contextual mapping, measurement, monitoring, risk response, and residual-risk management. It also emphasizes impacts on individuals, groups, organizations, communities, society, the environment, and the planet, which aligns with the affected-subject perspective introduced in Section 2.1. However, it is not used as the main structuring framework because the deliverable is aligned with ISO-style risk management phases and because Section 4 requires semantic application profiles that can be connected to ISO/IEC standards and EU regulatory obligations.

A different kind of adjacent resource is the MIT AI Risk Repository, developed by MIT FutureTech. Unlike the NIST AI RMF, it is not a risk management framework but a living database and meta-taxonomy of AI risks: it extracts and classifies 1,725 risks from 74 existing AI risk taxonomies and frameworks (Slattery et al., 2026). The Repository organizes these risks through two complementary taxonomies. The Causal Taxonomy classifies risks by their origins along three dimensions: the entity responsible (human or AI), the intentionality of the risk (intentional or unintentional), and its timing (pre-deployment or post-deployment). The Domain Taxonomy classifies risks by their effects across seven domains (discrimination and toxicity, privacy and security, misinformation, malicious actors and misuse, human-computer interaction, socioeconomic and environmental harms, and AI system safety, failures, and limitations) which are further divided into subdomains. The Repository is relevant to this deliverable for two reasons. First, it documents empirically that existing AI risk frameworks are fragmented and use inconsistent terminology, with individual frameworks covering only a fraction of the identified risk subdomains. This supports the premise of this deliverable that a shared semantic representation of AI risk is needed. Second, its taxonomies provide a research-based catalogue of risk types that can serve as a crosswalk source for the risk identification

vocabularies examined in Section 3, alongside the IBM AI Risk Atlas. However, the Repository is a classification of risks, not a risk management process: it supports the identification phase but does not address analysis against criteria, evaluation, treatment, or management-system documentation. It is therefore treated as an adjacent taxonomy resource rather than as part of the standards architecture.

Other non-ISO frameworks are also relevant for completeness, especially where they emphasize ethics, human rights, and societal impact. The UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence is important because it provides a global normative framework centred on human rights, human dignity, transparency, fairness, human oversight, safety, security, diversity, inclusiveness, and environmental flourishing (UNESCO, 2022). UNESCO describes the Recommendation as the first global standard on AI ethics, applicable to all UNESCO Member States. It also provides practical implementation tools, including the Readiness Assessment Methodology and the Ethical Impact Assessment. The Readiness Assessment Methodology helps Member States assess their preparedness to implement the Recommendation, while the Ethical Impact Assessment is a structured process that helps AI project teams, in collaboration with affected communities, identify and assess the impacts of an AI system and identify harm-prevention actions.

The OECD AI Principles are also relevant as a policy-level trustworthy AI framework (OECD, 2024). The OECD describes the Principles as promoting AI that is innovative, trustworthy, and respectful of human rights and democratic values. Their values-based principles include inclusive growth, sustainable development and well-being; human rights and democratic values, including fairness and privacy; transparency and explainability; robustness, security and safety; and accountability. These principles are not a risk management process in the ISO sense, but they are important because they provide a widely used international vocabulary for trustworthy AI and have influenced AI governance frameworks across jurisdictions.

These adjacent frameworks and resources expand the context of Section 2 without changing the methodological choice of the deliverable. ISO 31000, ISO/IEC 23894, IEC 31010, ISO/IEC 42001, and ISO/IEC 42005 remain the main standards-based architecture. The NIST AI RMF is treated as a complementary operational AI risk management framework. The MIT AI Risk Repository is treated as an adjacent taxonomy resource that provides empirical grounding and crosswalk material for risk identification. UNESCO's AI ethics tools and the OECD AI Principles are treated as adjacent governance and ethics frameworks. They are useful for completeness, comparison, and vocabulary alignment, but they are not adopted as the primary structure for the application profile.

Table 2.2b - Adjacent AI governance frameworks

Framework	Primary role	Main contribution	Relationship to this deliverable
NIST AI RMF	Voluntary AI risk management framework	Provides four operational functions: Govern, Map, Measure, and Manage. It also identifies trustworthy AI characteristics such as validity, reliability, safety, security, resilience, accountability, transparency, explainability, interpretability, privacy enhancement, and fairness with harmful bias managed.	Relevant as an operational comparison point, but not adopted as the primary structure because the deliverable follows the ISO risk management architecture.
MIT AI Risk Repository	Living database and meta-taxonomy of AI risks	Classifies 1,725 risks extracted from 74 frameworks through a Causal Taxonomy (entity, intent, timing) and a Domain Taxonomy (seven domains with subdomains); documents the fragmentation and partial coverage of existing AI risk frameworks.	Relevant as empirical motivation for shared semantic representation and as a crosswalk source for the risk identification taxonomies of Section 3; not a risk management process and not part of the standards architecture.
UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of AI	Global ethics and human-rights framework	Provides values, principles, policy areas, and implementation tools, including the Readiness Assessment Methodology and Ethical Impact Assessment.	Relevant for ethical and societal impact vocabulary, especially affected communities, human rights, dignity, fairness, inclusiveness, and harm-prevention actions.
OECD AI Principles	Policy-level trustworthy AI framework	Provides international principles for trustworthy AI, including human rights, democratic values, fairness, privacy, transparency, explainability, robustness, security, safety, and accountability.	Relevant as background governance vocabulary and for alignment with international AI policy language, but not a risk management lifecycle model.

Risk is not a single stable concept across the instruments under review. The standards provide a layered architecture: general risk management in ISO 31000, AI-specific risk management in ISO/IEC 23894, assessment techniques in IEC 31010, AI management system requirements in ISO/IEC 42001,

and AI system impact assessment in ISO/IEC 42005. Adjacent frameworks and resources such as the NIST AI RMF, the MIT AI Risk Repository, UNESCO's AI ethics instruments, and the OECD AI Principles broaden this landscape by adding operational, empirical, ethical, human-rights, and policy-oriented vocabularies, but they do not replace the ISO-based structure adopted in this deliverable.

EU regulations adopt fragments of this architecture unevenly and attach risk to different affected subjects, obligated actors, outputs, and procedural requirements. The central modelling problem is therefore not simply to define "risk," but to represent the relationships between risk sources, events, consequences, likelihood, affected subjects, assessment processes, techniques, controls, management-system documentation, impact-assessment outputs, and legal compliance artefacts. Section 3 addresses this task by examining semantic models capable of connecting these elements without collapsing their differences.

3 SEMANTIC RISK MANAGEMENT MODELS

The previous section established that risk management in AI and data regulation is a fragmented landscape: different standards organize the activity differently, EU regulations mandate fragments of that organization unevenly, and impact assessment exists as three distinct kinds of object depending on the perspective taken. Section 4 of this deliverable develops an application profile that operationalizes part of that landscape: concrete representations of risk management requirements for the AI Act. This application profile must be built on a semantic foundation. This section examines which existing semantic model is most appropriate as that foundation, and on what grounds. For an introduction to semantic web technologies and an overview over their role in as well as other approaches to compliance checking, please refer to deliverable 2.2 of this project (Lecat et al., 2026).

The choice of foundation matters beyond convenience. A semantic model carries assumptions about what risk is, what entities populate the domain, what relationships connect them, and what kinds of statements can be expressed. A foundation that is well-developed in cybersecurity but weak on data protection will distort downstream application profiles toward cybersecurity-shaped representations. A foundation tied to a single regulation will not extend cleanly to the cumulative compliance situation described in the previous section. The selection therefore needs to be made against explicit criteria rather than by default.

3.1 Methodology

This section evaluates candidate models against six criteria:

Lifecycle coverage. Does the model represent all four ISO-style risk management phases (identification, analysis, evaluation, treatment), or only some?

Scope. Is the model general enough to cover AI risk, data protection risk, cybersecurity risk, systemic risk, and operational risk together, or is it bound to a single domain?

Formal type. Is the model an RDF/OWL/SKOS vocabulary (the technical foundation required for Section 4's application profile), a machine-readable schema, a modelling language, or a knowledge base?

Coverage of affected subjects. Does the model represent affected subjects (organizations, individuals, groups, societies, legal interests) as first-class entities, or does it treat risk primarily in relation to organizational objectives?

Interoperability and extensibility. Does the model provide explicit mechanisms for extension via application profile, and does it connect to neighbouring vocabularies?

Legal and regulatory relevance. Does the model represent regulatory artefacts (DPIA, FRIA, conformity assessment outputs, technical documentation) and obligated/affected actor roles?

The remainder of the section examines candidate models against these criteria. Subsections 3.2 to 3.5 follow the four ISO-style phases used throughout the deliverable, examining which models

support each phase and how. Tables 3.1 and 3.2 consolidate the comparison; Table 3.3 lists related models identified during the survey but not retained in the main comparison, with reasons for exclusion. The closing subsection synthesizes the evaluation against the six criteria and identifies the foundation selected for Section 4.

The candidate models in the main comparison are:

- DPV/RISK (Pandit et al., 2024)
- AIRO (Golpayegani et al., 2022)
- VAIR (Golpayegani et al., 2023)
- IBM AI Risk Atlas (Bagehorn et al., 2025)
- Riskman (Gorczyca et al., 2025)
- UCO (Casey et al., 2018) (Casey et al., 2017)
- STIX 2.1 (OASIS, 2021)
- OSCAL (National Institute of Standards and Technology [NIST], 2021)
- Fenz/AURUM security ontology (Fenz & Ekelhart, 2009)
- CORAS (Lund et al., 2011)

AIRO and VAIR are treated separately, not as a single unit: AIRO is an OWL ontology providing the structural concepts for AI risk, while VAIR is a SKOS vocabulary providing controlled lists of AI risk sources, consequences, and impacts. They are designed to be used together, but they are different artefacts and contribute differently to the phases below.

3.2 Semantic models for risk identification

Risk identification concerns the representation of what risks exist, where they come from, what objects or subjects are affected, and what circumstances can give rise to unwanted outcomes. In the ISO-style process, this includes risk sources, potential events, assets, controls, consequences, and affected subjects.

DPV/RISK provides the broadest general support for risk identification. It contains concepts for risk, risk source, risk subject, threat source, consequence, impact, incident, control, and mitigation. It also includes taxonomies of potential risks, potential risk sources, technical risks, organizational risks, societal risks, legal risks, consequences, and impacts. The presence of explicit subject-related concepts is important against criterion 4 (affected subjects): DPV/RISK does represent affected subjects as a first-class concern, although the granularity of the affected-subject taxonomy is general rather than regulation-specific and will need refinement in the application profile of Section 4.

AIRO and VAIR together provide strong support for AI-specific risk identification. AIRO represents AI systems, risk sources, hazards, threats, misuse, consequences, impacts, vulnerabilities, and affected AI subjects. VAIR provides controlled vocabularies of AI-specific risk sources, including risks connected to data, models, organizational processes, performance, and system characteristics.

Their scope, however, is narrower than DPV/RISK: they are AI-oriented and do not extend natively to data protection, cybersecurity, or systemic risk identification.

Cybersecurity models support risk identification in their domain. UCO represents cyber objects, observables, incidents, and investigations with strong granularity. STIX 2.1 supports the identification of threats, vulnerabilities, attack patterns, indicators, threat actors, incidents, and courses of action. Both are strong on the cybersecurity-specific aspects of identification but do not provide a general representation of affected subjects beyond the cyber-asset perspective, and STIX 2.1 is a CTI exchange language rather than an RDF/OWL vocabulary.

Riskman identifies hazards and hazardous situations within medical-device risk management. CORAS identifies assets, threats, vulnerabilities, unwanted incidents, and threat scenarios within model-driven risk analysis for security-critical systems. The Fenz/AURUM security ontology identifies threats, vulnerabilities, and information assets within the information security domain. The IBM AI Risk Atlas provides a curated taxonomy of AI risks (covering accuracy, robustness, fairness, transparency, privacy, and related concerns) usable for AI risk identification, but it is a structured catalogue with associated tooling rather than a formal semantic vocabulary in the OWL/SKOS sense. OSCAL supports identification only indirectly, through its risk-and-finding structures within assessment results; it is not a risk identification vocabulary.

3.3 Semantic models for risk analysis

Risk analysis concerns the representation of the nature and level of risk. It includes likelihood, severity, consequence, impact, exposure, uncertainty, the effectiveness of existing controls, and potentially a derived risk level.

DPV/RISK provides broad support for risk analysis. It includes concepts for likelihood, severity, risk level, risk matrices, consequence, impact, incident metadata, and risk and impact taxonomies. This allows a risk to be analysed in relation to probability, seriousness, affected subjects, types of impact, and possible consequences. The risk matrix construct is particularly important because it supports the explicit comparison of likelihood and severity that the ISO 31000 process layer requires.

AIRO provides AI-specific structural support for risk analysis: it represents risk as being expressed through sources, consequences, impacts, likelihood, and severity. VAIR strengthens this by providing AI-specific categories of consequences and impacts, including bias, decreased robustness, decreased security, degraded accuracy, and other AI-relevant harms. Used together, they support analysis at a level of detail that DPV/RISK alone does not reach for AI-specific concerns.

The IBM AI Risk Atlas connects AI risks to evaluations, benchmarks, and mitigation patterns. It is useful for mapping AI risks to evaluation workflows and supports analysis-adjacent activity, but it is

not aligned with the ISO 31000 phase structure and does not provide explicit likelihood-severity-level vocabulary.

Cybersecurity models support analysis within their domain. UCO can represent the structural relationships among threats, incidents, malware, vulnerabilities, attack patterns, and courses of action. STIX 2.1 supports the analytical relationships needed for threat intelligence but does not provide an explicit risk-level construct. Neither is designed as a full risk analysis vocabulary with likelihood, severity, and risk criteria as first-class elements.

OSCAL supports analysis-adjacent activity through its risk, finding, and observation structures, which connect assessment results to identified risks. This is control-assessment analysis rather than risk-concept analysis: OSCAL analyses whether controls have been properly implemented and whether findings indicate open risks, rather than analysing risks in terms of likelihood and severity against criteria.

Riskman and Fenz/AURUM both provide strong analytical support within their respective domains (medical-device safety and information security). CORAS provides a structured analytical method, including likelihood and consequence estimations that can be visualized through CORAS risk diagrams. None of these is a general semantic vocabulary suitable as a cross-regulatory foundation.

3.4 Semantic models for risk evaluation

Risk evaluation concerns the comparison of analysed risks against criteria. It answers whether the risk is acceptable, tolerable, high, or low, and whether treatment is needed. This phase is the one where the standards architecture is least uniformly supported by the candidate models.

DPV/RISK provides the strongest general support. It includes concepts for risk criteria, risk level, risk evaluation, residual risk, risk matrices, and distinct levels of likelihood, severity, and risk. This makes it possible to represent the step where analysed risk is compared against criteria or thresholds, and to represent the residual risk that remains after treatment. The presence of explicit evaluation and residual risk constructs distinguishes DPV/RISK from most other models in the comparison, which represent risk levels or assessments without an explicit evaluation step.

AIRO and VAIR provide partial support for evaluation. They are strong for AI-specific risk classification and AI Act-oriented documentation, especially where the task is to determine whether an AI system is high-risk or whether a particular AI risk is associated with a source, consequence, likelihood, or severity. They are less general than DPV/RISK for representing risk criteria as a separate concept, residual risk after treatment, and evaluation decisions across regulatory domains.

Riskman provides strong support for evaluation within the medical-device domain. It formalizes risk management documentation and uses SHACL shapes to check completeness and conformity of the

documentation. The SHACL-based evaluation capability is methodologically valuable and has informed the design of the application profile in Section 4. However, Riskman's evaluation concepts are specific to medical-device safety and ISO 14971 and are not directly reusable for AI Act, GDPR, DSA, NIS2, DORA, or CRA application profiles.

OSCAL provides evaluation support in the control-assessment sense: it represents assessment results, findings, implemented controls, control effectiveness, and plans of action and milestones (POA&Ms). This is strong support for the evaluation of *control implementation* but does not provide a general vocabulary for the evaluation of *risk* against risk criteria.

CORAS provides evaluation support through its method, including the visualization of risk relationships and the comparison of estimated risks. It is a framework and modelling language rather than a reusable semantic vocabulary, which limits its role as a foundation for cross-regulatory application profiles.

UCO and STIX do not provide explicit risk evaluation support; their domain is threat representation rather than risk acceptability assessment. The IBM AI Risk Atlas supports evaluation-adjacent activity through risk ratings within its catalogue but does not provide an explicit evaluation construct comparable to DPV/RISK.

3.5 Semantic models for risk treatment

Risk treatment concerns the representation of measures selected to address risk: controls, safeguards, mitigation measures, treatment plans, residual risk, implementation status, and monitoring. This is the phase where comparison between DPV/RISK and OSCAL is most substantive, because both are designed to represent controls in detail.

DPV/RISK provides strong support for risk treatment. It includes risk controls, mitigation measures, incident mitigation measures, and connections between risks, impacts, consequences, and controls. It also includes residual risk, which is important for representing the outcome after treatment. The treatment vocabulary is integrated with the rest of the model, so a control can be linked to the risk it addresses, the consequence it mitigates, and the affected subject it protects.

OSCAL provides strong support for treatment and control documentation, arguably more detailed than DPV/RISK in this specific phase. It is designed for representing implemented controls, control baselines, assessment plans, assessment results, and POA&Ms. OSCAL is especially strong where the task is documenting and automating control-based compliance, and it is widely adopted in the security and privacy controls community. Its limitation as a foundation for this deliverable is not that it represents controls poorly - it represents them very well - but that it is control-centric rather than risk-concept-centric. OSCAL's risk and finding structures sit alongside controls but do not provide the general risk vocabulary (sources, events, consequences, likelihood, severity, evaluation) needed

for the upstream phases. OSCAL is also a schema set (XML/JSON/YAML), not an RDF/OWL/SKOS vocabulary, which limits its direct usability as a semantic foundation in the sense required by Section 4.

AIRO and VAIR provide AI-specific treatment support. They can represent controls, documentation, and AI governance concepts relevant to AI systems. VAIR includes AI-specific control and documentation vocabulary, which makes it useful as a complement to DPV/RISK for AI Act-oriented applications. Their treatment vocabulary is narrower in scope than DPV/RISK's because it is AI-focused.

Riskman provides strong treatment support within the medical-device safety context, representing mitigation arguments and safety documentation that align with ISO 14971 risk management files. Fenz/AURUM provides treatment support within information security, modelling threats, vulnerabilities, controls, ratings, and ISO 27002-style controls. CORAS provides treatment support within its method, representing risk treatments diagrammatically. None of these is suitable as the primary cross-regulatory treatment vocabulary.

STIX 2.1 provides partial treatment support through courses of action in cybersecurity threat intelligence. UCO supports treatment indirectly through cyber-domain extensions and mappings. The IBM AI Risk Atlas links risks to mitigation patterns and recommended actions, which provides treatment-adjacent support but does not constitute a treatment vocabulary in the semantic-web sense.

3.6 Consolidated comparison

The phase-by-phase analysis can be consolidated into two views: a coverage matrix across the four ISO-style phases (Table 3.1) and a detailed feature comparison (Table 3.2). Related models identified during the survey but not retained in the main comparison are listed in Table 3.3, grouped by reason for exclusion.

Table 3.1 - Semantic risk management models: coverage of ISO-style phases

Legend: + strong and explicit support; ± partial, indirect; – weak support or not a primary design goal. The *Scope* column reflects criterion 2: *general* models address risk across multiple domains; *domain-restricted* models are confined to a single domain (medical devices, information security, cybersecurity, financial services, etc.). The *Formal type* column reflects criterion 3: *RDF/OWL/SKOS* indicates a semantic-web vocabulary; *schema* indicates a structured machine-readable format; *language/method* indicates a modelling framework rather than a reusable vocabulary; *catalogue* indicates a curated taxonomy with tooling.

Model	Identification	Analysis	Evaluation	Treatment	Scope	Formal type	Openly available
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DPV/RISK	+	+	+	+	General (AI, data protection, security, societal)	RDF/OWL/SKOS	+
AIRO	+	+	±	±	AI-specific	RDF/OWL	+
VAIR	+	+	±	+	AI-specific	SKOS	+
IBM AI Risk Atlas	+	±	±	±	AI-specific	Catalogue with tooling	+
Riskman	+	+	+	+	Medical-device-specific	RDF/OWL + SHACL	+
UCO	+	±	-	-	Cybersecurity-specific	RDF/OWL	+
STIX 2.1	+	±	-	±	Cybersecurity-specific	Schema (CTI language)	+
OSCAL	±	±	+	+	Security/privacy controls	Schema (XML/JSON/YAML)	+
Fenz / AURUM	+	+	±	+	Information security	RDF/OWL (academic)	+
CORAS	+	+	±	±	Security-critical systems	Modelling language/method	±

The matrix makes two findings visible. First, only DPV/RISK combines strong support across all four phases with general scope and an RDF/OWL/SKOS formal type. Second, Riskman matches DPV/RISK on phase coverage but is restricted to a single domain; the comparison is not "DPV/RISK is more complete" but "DPV/RISK is general where Riskman is domain-restricted."

Table 3.2 - Detailed comparison of candidate models

Model	Formal type	Main domain	Main strengths	Main limitations for this deliverable
DPV/RISK	RDF/OWL/SKOS vocabulary	Privacy, data protection, AI governance, risk management	Covers risk sources, consequences, impacts, likelihood, severity, risk levels, controls, incidents, mitigation, residual risk, legal and societal risks; explicit extension via	Broad and lightweight; AI Act- and FRIA-specific concepts require specialization in application profiles

			application profiles; connects to DPV main vocabulary	
AIRO	RDF/OWL ontology	AI risk and AI Act compliance	Structural AI risk concepts: AI systems, risk sources, hazards, threats, misuse, consequences, impacts, vulnerabilities	Narrower than DPV/RISK; strongest as AI-specific complement; less general for non-AI domains
VAIR	SKOS vocabulary	AI risk source taxonomy	Controlled vocabularies for AI-specific risk sources, consequences, impacts, and controls	Vocabulary rather than ontology; designed to be used with AIRO
PrOnto	RDF/OWL legal/privacy ontology	GDPR and legal compliance	Strong for GDPR actors, roles, processing, rights, duties, obligations, DPIA-relevant concepts, and legal reasoning	Not designed as an ISO-style risk management lifecycle ontology. The formal model is not Openly available
IBM AI Risk Atlas	Catalogue with associated tooling	AI governance and foundation-model risk	Curated taxonomy of AI risks across accuracy, robustness, fairness, transparency, privacy, and related concerns; links risks to evaluations and mitigation patterns	Not a formal RDF/OWL/SKOS vocabulary; structured catalogue rather than ontology
Riskman	RDF/OWL ontology with SHACL shapes	Medical-device risk management	Full formalization of risk management documentation; SHACL-based completeness checking; strong for hazards, mitigation, and validation	Domain-specific to medical devices and ISO 14971-style safety files
UCO	RDF/OWL ontology family	Cybersecurity	Strong foundation for cyber objects, incidents, investigations, and cyber-domain data integration	Not a full risk lifecycle ontology; limited evaluation and treatment modelling
STIX 2.1	Machine-readable CTI language (schema)	Cyber threat intelligence	Strong for threats, vulnerabilities, attack patterns, indicators, incidents, reports, and courses of action	Not an RDF/OWL vocabulary; not an ISO-style risk management ontology; weak on

				risk criteria and residual risk
OSCAL	Schema set (XML/JSON/YAML)	Security and privacy controls	Strong for controls, baselines, assessment plans, assessment results, POA&Ms, evidence, and compliance automation; widely adopted	Schema-based rather than RDF-based; control-centric rather than risk-concept-centric
Fenz / AURUM	Academic security ontology and decision-support framework	Information security risk management	Strong for threat, vulnerability, controls, threat probability, risk rating, and ISO 27002-style control formalization	Established but dating from 2009–2010; security-specific; less directly aligned with current AI and data regulation
CORAS	Model-driven risk analysis language and framework	Security-critical systems	Strong for assets, threats, vulnerabilities, unwanted incidents, threat scenarios, and risk diagrams	Method and modelling language rather than a reusable RDF vocabulary; limited direct legal interoperability

Table 3.3 - Related models identified but not retained in the main comparison

The following models surfaced during the survey of the landscape but were not retained in the main phase-by-phase comparison. They are grouped by the reason for their exclusion. They remain relevant for the deliverable as sources of specific concepts that may be mapped or referenced in the application profile of Section 4, even if they are not used as the primary foundation.

Reason for exclusion	Related model	Description and relevance
Foundational rather than operational	COVER	Foundational ontology of value and risk. Strong conceptual grounding; not an operational lifecycle vocabulary.
	BFO-based risk ontology	Foundational analysis of risk grounded in Basic Formal Ontology. Conceptual rather than application-profile-ready.
	Open Risk DOAM / BMRO / RFO	Risk-model, business-model risk, and risk-function ontologies. Meta-level and finance/business-oriented.
	FIBO	Financial business ontology. Relevant for financial exposure and assessment concepts; sector-specific.

Domain-restricted beyond this deliverable	Container Security Risk Ontology (CSRO)	Security risk identification for container deployments in OT contexts. Highly technical and domain-specific.
	NORIA-O	Anomaly detection and incident management in ICT systems. Operations-oriented rather than risk-lifecycle-oriented.
Tool or workflow-bound	Spyderisk	Uses ontologies of harm, risk, misbehaviour, controls, and automated risk analysis. Tool/knowledge-base-oriented; less established as a reusable cross-domain vocabulary.
	MITRE ATLAS	AI adversary tactics and threat knowledge base. Strong for AI threat identification; embedded in MITRE tooling.
AI requirements- or principles-oriented	TAIR	Trustworthy AI requirements ontology. Useful for AI Act and standards requirement crosswalks.
	AIPO	AI principles and ethics ontology. Useful for ethical-principles comparison.
	AICat	AI-system catalogue model for AI Act registries. Useful for AI system documentation and registry-style descriptions.
Quantitative or research-prototype	Open FAIR / FAIR ontology tradition	Quantitative information security risk analysis tradition. Strong for analysis; not usually used as a semantic lifecycle vocabulary for legal application profiles.
	Process-aware risk propagation ontology	Models risk propagation through processes and objects. Research prototype rather than general regulatory documentation.

3.7 Selection of the semantic foundation

Returning to the six evaluation criteria stated previously:

On lifecycle coverage (criterion 1), DPV/RISK and Riskman are the only models that provide strong support across all four ISO-style phases. The other models cover one to three phases adequately and the remaining phases partially or not at all.

On scope (criterion 2), DPV/RISK is the only model in the main comparison that is general across AI, data protection, cybersecurity, and societal risk. Riskman is restricted to medical devices; AIRO and VAIR to AI; PrOnto to GDPR; UCO, STIX, OSCAL, Fenz/AURUM, and CORAS to cybersecurity or security-critical systems.

On formal type (criterion 3), DPV/RISK is a mature RDF/OWL/SKOS vocabulary suitable for the application profile development in Section 4. AIRO, VAIR, UCO, Riskman, and Fenz/AURUM are also RDF/OWL or SKOS, but with the scope limitations noted. STIX 2.1 and OSCAL are schema-based

rather than RDF-based, which limits their suitability as foundations even where their coverage is strong. The IBM AI Risk Atlas is a catalogue with tooling rather than a formal semantic vocabulary. CORAS is a modelling language and method rather than a vocabulary.

On coverage of affected subjects (criterion 4), DPV/RISK represents affected subjects as a first-class concern through its risk subject and impact taxonomies. AIRO represents affected AI subjects but at a lower level of granularity for non-AI domains. The cybersecurity models represent affected assets rather than affected persons or societies. Specialization for fundamental-rights subjects and societal subjects, in particular, will need to be elaborated in the application profile regardless of the foundation chosen.

On interoperability and extensibility (criterion 5), DPV/RISK is explicitly designed for extension via application profiles and connects to the broader DPV vocabulary, which itself covers data protection concepts central to this deliverable. AIRO and VAIR are designed to interoperate with DPV and have published alignments with it. OSCAL has strong tooling but limited interoperability with RDF-based vocabularies. The cybersecurity models interoperate within their own communities but require additional work to connect to AI and data protection vocabularies.

On legal and regulatory relevance (criterion 6), DPV/RISK includes legal risk concepts and connects to DPV's broader legal vocabulary. AIRO and VAIR include AI Act-relevant concepts. None of the candidate models provides complete out-of-the-box coverage of FRIA, DPIA, or AI Act technical documentation as defined in regulation; specialization is required in all cases.

The selection follows from this comparison. **DPV/RISK is adopted as the primary foundation for the application profile in Section 4**, on the grounds that it combines strong lifecycle coverage, general scope across the relevant domains, a mature RDF/OWL/SKOS formal type, explicit treatment of affected subjects, designed-in extensibility, and connection to a broader legal and data protection vocabulary. **AIRO and VAIR are adopted as AI-specific complements**, to provide the structural and vocabulary detail that DPV/RISK does not natively cover at AI-specific granularity.

DPV/RISK is the model that best satisfies the six criteria stated at the outset of this section. The areas where DPV/RISK requires specialization, granular affected-subject taxonomies for fundamental-rights and societal subjects, FRIA-specific concepts, AI Act-specific concepts that go beyond AIRO/VAIR, and SHACL-based completeness shapes, are addressed in Section 4 through the development of the application profiles. The selection of a foundation that requires specialization is normal in semantic engineering: the alternative would be a model that pretended to cover all regulations natively, which would either be too narrow in practice or would impose a single regulation's worldview on the others.

Section 4 develops this application profile, starting with the extraction of requirements from the AI Act, examining how those requirements can be operationalized through the standards architecture described in previous sections, and encoding the result in DPV/RISK and SHACL shapes for compliance checking.

4 APPLICATION PROFILE

Application profiles generally define a set of (meta-)data elements for a particular application. The application profile presented in this section is based on the Data Privacy Vocabulary (see previous section), and defines the use of DPV concepts for the machine-readable documentation of a risk management system in compliance with Article 9 of the AI Act. Hence, for a given risk management system documented through DPV, the SHACL shapes introduced here can support the automatic verification of compliance with the requirements of the AI Act.

SHACL (Shapes Constraint Language) shapes are a W3C standard for defining and validating the structure, constraints, and integrity rules that RDF data must conform to within a specific application context. In an application profile, they serve as machine-readable specifications that formally express which properties are required or optional, what datatypes or value ranges are permitted, and how resources must be structured, enabling automated validation of data against the profile's rules.

4.1 Methodology

The development of the application profile follows the Linked Open Terms (LOT) methodology (Poveda-Villalón et al., 2022).

1. *Ontology Requirement Specification*: Requirements for the risk management process are identified from Article 9 of the AI Act.
1. *Ontology Implementation*: The requirements extracted in step 1 are then mapped against the risk management process structure of ISO 23894 and ISO 31000. The Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV) is selected as a basis for the application profile (see section 4). Existing DPV concepts are then used to develop a SHACL shape that satisfies the ISO approach (if existing) to each requirement of Article 9 of the AI Act.
2. *Ontology Evaluation*: For the purpose of evaluation, both a compliant and a non-compliant test semantic risk management model have been created to verify the correct behavior of developed SHACL constraints.
3. *Ontology Publication*: The resulting application profile, in the form of a SHACL file, is available on Github². An interactive web application, enabling the upload and checking of semantic risk management model files, is available on Streamlit³.
4. *Ontology Maintenance*: A second version of this deliverable is foreseen by the end of 2027. This will include a review and potential update to the application profile.

² <https://github.com/FabianLinde/ai-act-art9-compliance-checker/blob/main/rules.shacl>

³ <https://aiactart9compliancechecker.linkeddata.es/>

4.2 Requirement extraction from AIA

Article 9 of the EU AI Act requires providers of high-risk AI systems to establish a continuous, iterative risk management system throughout the system's entire lifecycle. This process involves identifying and evaluating foreseeable risks to health, safety, and fundamental rights, including those arising from intended use, potential misuse, and post-market monitoring.

Providers must address these risks through a specific hierarchy of measures: first by eliminating or reducing risks through design and development, then by implementing mitigation controls, and finally by providing comprehensive information to deployers regarding any residual risks. To ensure compliance, the AI system must undergo rigorous testing against defined metrics before being placed on the market. Additionally, the risk management process must specifically account for potential adverse impacts on minors and other vulnerable groups, though providers may integrate these requirements into existing risk management frameworks established under other Union laws.

The following requirements have been extracted from Article 9:

- R.1 Establish RMS (Art. 9(1))
- R.2 Implement RMS (Art. 9(1))
- R.3 Document RMS (Art. 9(1))
- R.4 Maintain RMS (Art. 9(1))
- R.5 RMS as continuous iterative process (Art. 9(2))
- R.6 RMS to cover entire lifecycle of AI system (Art. 9(2))
- R.7 Regular systematic review of RMS (Art. 9(2))
- R.8 Regular updating of RMS (Art. 9(2))
- R.9 Identification of risk to health, safety or fundamental rights when AI system is used in accordance with its intended purpose (Art. 9(2)(a))
- R.10 Analysis of risk to health, safety or fundamental rights when AI system is used in accordance with its intended purpose (Art. 9(2)(a))
- R.11 Estimation of risks that may emerge when AI system is used in accordance with its intended purpose (Art. 9(2)(b))
- R.12 Estimation of risks that may emerge under conditions of reasonably foreseeable misuse (Art. 9(2)(b))
- R.13 Evaluation of risks that may emerge when AI system is used in accordance with its intended purpose (Art. 9(2)(b))
- R.14 Evaluation of risks that may emerge under conditions of reasonably foreseeable misuse
- R.15 Evaluation of other risks possibly arising (Art. 9(2)(c))
- R.16 Risk management measures designed to address the risks identified (Art. 9(2)(d))
- R.17 Residual risks must be acceptable (Art. 9(5))
- R.18 Reduction/elimination of risks as far as technically feasible (Art. 9(5)(a))

- R.19 Implementation of adequate mitigation and control measures addressing risks that cannot be eliminated (Art. 9(5)(b))
- R.20 Provision of information under Art. 13 (Art. 9(5)(c))
- R.21 Provision of training to deployers (where appropriate) (Art. 9(5)(c))
- R.22 Consideration to expertise of deployer (Art. 9(5))
- R.23 Consideration to context of AI system (Art. 9(5))
- R.24 Testing of AI system to identify most appropriate risk management measures (Art. 9(6))
- R.25 Testing before market placement (Art. 9(8))
- R.26 Consideration of impact on persons under age of 18 (Art. 9(9))
- R.27 Consideration of impact on other vulnerable groups (Art. 9(9))

Each of these requirements has been given a unique identifier (R.x).

4.3 Examination of requirement operationalization in ISO standards

In the next step, ISO 23894 (for guidance on risk management in AI) and ISO 31000 (for general risk management guidelines) are consulted to guide the operationalization for each of the requirements (R.1 - R.27) identified in Article 9 AIA.

For example, requirement R.10 (“Analysis of risk to health, safety or fundamental rights when AI system is used in accordance with its intended purpose”) corresponds to section 6.4.3 *Risk Analysis* in ISO 23894. This section requires two steps: the *Assessment of consequences* (ISO 23894, 6.4.3.2) and the *Assessment of likelihood* (ISO 23894, 6.4.3.3). Therefore, requirement R.10 is operationalized by two processes, which are also given unique identifiers (O.x) which help to clarify the structure of the developed SHACL constraints.

See table 4.1 for an overview of operationizations of each requirement.

4.4 Compilation of documentation elements mandatory/optional for compliance

Each operationalization (O.1 - O.27) is then turned into a formal requirement that must be satisfied by a compliant risk management system.

For example, considering the two operationalizations O.10.1 and O.10.2 for requirement R.10 discussed above are then formalized as follows:

- O.10.1 → “Every consequence must have exactly one severity”
- O.10.2 → “Every consequence must have exactly on likelihood”

Table 4.1 - Overview of AIA Art. 9 requirements, operationalization in ISO 23894 and ISO 31000 standards, their translation into formal requirements, alongside identifiers for requirements and operationalizations.

Article 9 Clause	R.#	AIA Requirement	O.#	Operationalization in ISO 31000/23894	Formal Requirement
(1)	R.1	<u>Establish</u> RMS	O.1	N/A (Entire ISO 23894)	<u>High-Risk AI System</u> must <u>have</u> ≥ 1 <u>Risk Management System</u>
(1)	R.2	<u>Implement</u> RMS	O.2	Implementation (ISO 31000, 5.5)	<u>Risk Management System</u> must <u>have</u> ≥ 1 <u>Risk Assessment</u>
(1)	R.3	<u>Document</u> RMS	O.3	Recording and reporting (ISO 23894, 6.7)	[Covered by existence of semantic web documentation as prerequisite for application profile.]
(1)	R.4	<u>Maintain</u> RMS	O.4	Continually improving (ISO 31000, 5.7.2)	N/A (See limitations, section 4.7)
(2)	R.5	RMS as <u>continuous iterative</u> process	O.5	Continually improving (ISO 31000, 5.7.2)	N/A (See limitations, section 4.7)
(2)	R.6	RMS to cover <u>entire lifecycle</u> of AI system	O.6	Risk management and AI system life cycle (ISO 23894, Annex C)	N/A (See limitations, section 4.7)
(2)	R.7	Regular systematic <u>review</u> of RMS	O.7	Monitoring and review (ISO 31000, 6.6)	N/A (See limitations, section 4.7)
(2)	R.8	Regular <u>updating</u> of RMS	O.8	Adapting (ISO 31000, 5.7.1)	N/A (See limitations, section 4.7)
(2)(a)	R.9	<u>Identification</u> of risk to health, safety or fundamental rights when AI system is used in	O.9	Risk identification (ISO 23894, 6.4.2)	<u>Risk Assessment</u> must <u>have</u> ≥ 1 <u>Risk Identification</u>

		accordance with its intended purpose			
			O.9.1	Identification of assets and their value (ISO 23894, 6.4.2.2).	[No asset identification necessary, as AIA Art. 9 requires only consideration of risks to health, safety or fundamental rights. Reflected in O.9.6]
			O.9.2	Identification of risk sources (ISO 23894, 6.4.2.3)	<u>Risk must have ≥ 1 Risk Source</u>
			O.9.3	Identification of potential events and outcomes (ISO 23894, 6.4.2.4)	<u>Risk Identification must identify ≥ 1 Risk</u>
			O.9.4	Identification of controls (ISO 23894, 6.4.2.5)	<u>Risk must have ≥ 1 Risk Control</u> [cf. O.19]
			O.9.5	Identification of consequences (ISO 23894, 6.4.2.6)	<u>Risk must have ≥ 1 Consequence on Health, Safety or Fundamental Rights</u>

(2)(a)	R.10	<u>Analysis</u> of risk to health, safety or fundamental rights when AI system is used in accordance with its intended purpose	O.10.1	Assessment of consequences (ISO 23894, 6.4.3.2)	<u>Consequence</u> must <u>have</u> = 1 <u>Severity</u>
			O.10.2	Assessment of likelihood (ISO 23894, 6.4.3.3)	<u>Consequence</u> must <u>have</u> = 1 <u>Likelihood</u>
(2)(b)	R.11	<u>Estimation</u> of risks that may emerge when AI system is used in accordance with its intended purpose	O.11	Risk evaluation (ISO 31000, 6.4.4)	[Assuming estimation = evaluation, and every risk must be evaluated (despite separation of requirement in several clauses)] <u>Risk</u> must <u>have</u> \geq 1 <u>Risk Evaluation</u>
(2)(b)	R.12	<u>Evaluation</u> of risks that may emerge when AI system is used in accordance with its intended purpose	O.13	Risk evaluation (ISO 31000, 6.4.4)	
(2)(b)	R.13	<u>Estimation</u> of risks that may emerge under conditions of reasonably foreseeable misuse	O.12	Risk evaluation (ISO 31000, 6.4.4)	
(2)(b)	R.14	<u>Evaluation</u> of risks that may emerge under conditions of reasonably foreseeable misuse	O.14	Risk evaluation (ISO 31000, 6.4.4)	
(2)(c)	R.15	<u>Evaluation</u> of other risks possibly arising	O.15	Risk evaluation (ISO 31000, 6.4.4)	
(2)(d)	R.16	Risk management measures designed to <u>address</u> the risks identified	O.16	Risk treatment (ISO 23894, 6.5)	<u>Risk</u> must <u>have</u> \geq 1 <u>Risk Treatment</u>

(5)	R.17	<u>Residual risks</u> must be acceptable	O.17	Part of Risk treatment (ISO 31000, 6.5.1)	<u>Risk must have ≥ 0 Residual Risk AND Residual Risk must be acceptable</u>
(5)(b)	R.19	Implementation of adequate <u>mitigation</u> and <u>control</u> measures addressing risks that cannot be eliminated	O.19	Risk treatment (ISO 23894, 6.5)	<u>Risk must have ≥ 1 Risk Control</u> [cf. O.9.4]
(5)(c)	R.20	Provision of information under Art. 13	O.20	N/A	<u>High-Risk AI System must have ≥ 1 Information Provision to Deployer</u>
(5)(c)	R.21	Provision of training to deployers (where appropriate)	O.21	N/A	<u>High-Risk AI System must have = 1 Provider AND Provider must Provide Training to Deployer</u>
(5)	R.22	Consideration of expertise of deployer	O.22	External and internal context (ISO 23894, 6.3.3) [Not explicit]	N/A (<i>See limitations, section 4.7</i>)
(5)	R.23	Consideration of context of AI system	O.23	External and internal context (ISO 23894, 6.3.3)	N/A (<i>See limitations, section 4.7</i>)
(6)	R.24	Testing of AI system to identify most appropriate risk management measures	O.24	N/A	N/A (<i>See limitations, section 4.7</i>)
(8)	R.25	Testing before market placement	O.25	N/A	N/A (<i>See limitations, section 4.7</i>)

(9)	R.26	Consideration of impact on persons under age of 18	O.26	External and internal context (ISO 23894, 6.3.3) [Not explicit]	N/A (See limitations, section 4.7)
(9)	R.27	Consideration of impact on other vulnerable groups	O.27	External and internal context (ISO 23894, 6.3.3) [Not explicit]	N/A (See limitations, section 4.7)

4.5 Translation to existing DPV concepts

In this step, the terms contained in the formalized requirements are translated into existing concepts in DPV.

Table 4.2 - Translation of terms into DPV concepts

Natural Language	DPV Concepts
Consequence	dpv:Consequence
Fundamental Rights	eu:EUFundamentalRightsImpact
Health	risk:Health
High-Risk AI System	eu-aiact:HighRiskAISystem
identify	risk:identifies
Information Provision to Deployer	eu-aiact:InstructionsForUse
Likelihood	dpv:Likelihood
on	dpv:hasConsequenceOn
Provide	dpv:hasOrganisationalMeasure
Provider	eu-aiact:AIProvider
Residual Risk	dpv:ResidualRisk
Risk	dpv:Risk
Risk Assessment	risk:RiskAssessment
Risk Control	risk:RiskControl
Risk Evaluation	risk:RiskEvaluation
Risk Identification	risk:RiskIdentification
Risk Management System	risk:RiskManagement
Risk Source	risk:RiskSource
Risk Treatment	risk:RiskTreatment
RiskIdentification	risk:RiskIdentification

Natural Language	DPV Concepts
Safety	risk:Safety
Severity	dpv:Severity
Training to Deployer	eu-aiact:TrainingForDeployer ⁴

4.6 Encoding in SHACL shapes

Finally, the formal requirements for each operationalization, using the translations established in the previous steps, are used to establish the SHACL constraints.

```

@prefix sh: <http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#> .
@prefix dpv: <http://w3id.org/dpv#> .
@prefix risk: <https://w3id.org/dpv/risk#> .
@prefix eu-aiact: <https://w3id.org/dpv/legal/eu/aiact#> .

ex:HighRiskAISystem
  a sh:NodeShape ;
  sh:targetClass eu-aiact:HighRiskAISystem ;

# 0.1
sh:property [
  sh:path risk:hasRiskManagement ;
  sh:minCount 1 ;
  sh:class risk:RiskManagement ;
  sh:node ex:RiskManagementShape ;
] .

ex:RiskManagementShape
  a sh:NodeShape ;
  sh:targetClass risk:RiskManagement ;

# 0.2
sh:property [
  sh:path risk:hasRiskAssessment ;
  sh:minCount 1 ;
  sh:class risk:RiskAssessment ;
  sh:node ex:RiskAssessmentShape ;
] .

```

⁴ This concept has been proposed to the DPV Community Group and is currently under review.

```
ex:RiskAssessmentShape
  a sh:NodeShape ;
  sh:targetClass risk:RiskAssessment ;

# 0.9.1
sh:property [
  sh:path risk:hasRiskIdentification ;
  sh:minCount 1 ;
  sh:class risk:RiskIdentification ;
  sh:node ex:RiskIdentificationShape ;
] .
```

```
ex:RiskIdentificationShape
  a sh:NodeShape ;
  sh:targetClass risk:RiskIdentification ;

# 0.9.1.3
sh:property [
  sh:path risk:identifies ;
  sh:minCount 1 ;
  sh:class dpv:Risk ;
  sh:node ex:RiskShape ;
] ;

# 0.9.1.4
sh:property [
  sh:path risk:identifies ;
  sh:minCount 1 ;
  sh:class dpv:RiskControl ;
] .
```

```
ex:RiskShape
  a sh:NodeShape ;
  sh:targetClass risk:Risk ;

# 0.9.1.2
sh:property [
  sh:path risk:hasRiskSource ;
  sh:minCount 1 ;
  sh:class risk:RiskSource ; ] ;

# 0.9.1.5, 0.10.1, 0.10.2
sh:property [
  sh:path dpv:hasConsequence ;

  sh:qualifiedValueShape [
    sh:class dpv:Consequence ;
```

```
# 0.9.1.5
sh:property [
  sh:path dpv:hasConsequenceOn ;
  sh:or (
    [ sh:class risk:Health ]
    [ sh:class risk:Safety ]
    [ sh:class eu:EUFundamentalRightsImpact ]
  ) ;
  sh:minCount 1 ;
] ;

# 0.10.1
sh:property [
  sh:path dpv:hasSeverity ;
  sh:minCount 1 ;
  sh:class dpv:Severity ;
] ;

# 0.10.2
sh:property [
  sh:path dpv:hasLikelihood ;
  sh:minCount 1 ;
  sh:class dpv:Likelihood ;
] ;
] ;

# 0.16
sh:property [
  sh:path risk:hasRiskTreatment ;
  sh:minCount 1 ;
  sh:class risk:RiskTreatment ;
] ;

# 0.19
sh:property [
  sh:path risk:hasRiskControl ;
  sh:minCount 1 ;
  sh:class risk:RiskControl ;
] ;

# 0.11 - 0.15
sh:property [
  sh:path risk:hasRiskEvaluation ;
  sh:minCount 1 ;
  sh:class risk:RiskEvaluation ;
] .
```

4.7 Limitations

Turning legal requirements into semantic resources generally involves limitations, and these apply here as well.

First, not all requirements can adequately be represented in documentational format, whether machine-readable or not. For instance, AI Act Article 9(5) requires that “due consideration shall be given to the technical knowledge, experience, education, the training to be expected by the deployer”. While documentation might include a tickbox or similar for “due consideration”, whether this consideration was actually given can neither be covered by the documentation nor by any automated verification based on it.

Second, not all concepts present in the regulation and hence necessary for compliance checking will be covered by existing semantic resources. As concepts and meanings differ between jurisdictions, pieces of regulation or simply over time, consistent semantic modelling is difficult to impossible.

In order to address these difficulties, the application profile developed here is limited in scope to the provisions in paragraphs 1 to 4 of Article 9 of the AI Act, as well as paragraph 5 up to including point (c). Excluded are the final subparagraph of paragraph 5, as well as paragraphs 6 to 10. The exclusion is based on the observation that the provisions in the excluded paragraphs mostly concern organisational measures that are adjacent, but not integral to the risk management system, and their compliance can therefore not be modelled through semantic web technologies.

5 CONCLUSION

The work presented in this deliverable provides a systematic approach to navigating the overlapping compliance obligations of the AI Act, GDPR, and other systemic frameworks like NIS2 and DORA. A central achievement is the conceptual analysis that bridges the "harm-oriented" tradition of EU law with the "deviation-from-objectives" tradition of international ISO standards. By identifying the "affected subject" (i.e. the individual, group, or society bearing the consequences of risk) as a critical analytical link, the deliverable enables organizations to align their internal risk management with external legal protections.

5.1 Semantic Foundations and Application Profile

Through a structured evaluation of eleven existing models, DPV/RISK was selected as the primary semantic foundation for this work due to its maturity, broad scope across multiple domains, and explicit representation of affected subjects. To address specific AI risks such as bias and degraded accuracy, the framework incorporates AIRO and VAIR as specialized complements. These foundations support the creation of an application profile that operationalizes the risk management requirements of Article 9 of the AI Act. By translating these legal mandates into SHACL shapes, the deliverable provides a mechanism for automated completeness checking, allowing organizations to verify that their risk documentation meets both regulatory and standards-based criteria.

5.2 Risks Beyond Regulations and Standards

Despite the robustness of current models, certain emerging risks fall outside the immediate scope of existing harmonized standards and regulations. These include long-term societal shifts, such as the erosion of democratic agency or large-scale labor market displacement, which are difficult to capture in iterative, product-centric risk management systems. Additionally, the environmental impacts and energy consumption of large-scale AI models are increasingly recognized as significant risks that require further semantic elaboration and representation in future frameworks. These questions will also be addressed, through the application of anticipatory ethics among others, in work package 3 of this project.

5.3 Future Work

The HARNES project will continue to refine these models in subsequent versions, with several key directions for future research.

Version 2 of this deliverable (due in December 2027) will examine the expansion of the regulatory scope by developing dedicated application profiles for other instruments, such as the GDPR. Furthermore, version 2 will apply the application profile presented in this deliverable to at least two

case studies, with one use case being based on a high-risk AI system under Annex I and the other on a high-risk AI system under Annex III of the AI Act. Other deliverables in this project will foreseeably utilize the outputs of this deliverable, such as the tools for governance of data and AI services to be presented in deliverable 2.3, and the impact assessments and domain-specific analyses developed in deliverables 3.1 to 3.5 of work package 3 of this project.

Beyond the concrete contributions of the second version of this deliverable, future work will focus on enhancing tooling to integrate SHACL-based validation logic into user-friendly applications, supporting SMEs in conducting automated compliance checks. Finally, the project aims to support the AI Act's requirement for "continuous and iterative" risk management by exploring methods for dynamic risk monitoring and the integration of post-market data into existing semantic models.

DECLARATION OF USE OF AI-ASSISTED TECHNOLOGIES

The authors used Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies, the free versions of OpenAI's ChatGPT and Anthropic's Claude, for language assistance such as spelling and grammar checking, and for editing the form of this manuscript with no additions to its content. All technical content, experimental results, and scientific claims were verified and are the responsibility of the authors.

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